

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16744659>

Abstract. *This article discusses the relevance of the formation of professional pedagogical competencies of future primary school teachers. It analyzes the system of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the preparation for teaching. It also emphasizes the importance of using modern pedagogical approaches and innovative methods. The study offers practical recommendations and effective methodological approaches. The article outlines the scientific and theoretical foundations aimed at improving the quality of pedagogical education.*

Keywords: *primary school, pedagogical competence, teacher training, innovative methods, quality of education.*

In the 21st century, the educational process is developing rapidly. A modern school teacher is required not only to have in-depth knowledge of his subject, but also to have many other competencies, such as pedagogical skills, didactic approach, effective use of innovative technologies, mastery of communicative and information technologies. In particular, the professional pedagogical competencies of a primary school teacher are a decisive factor in the formation of the initial knowledge, skills and qualifications of the younger generation. Professional pedagogical competence is the ability of a teacher to effectively organize his professional activities, provide education taking into account the individual characteristics of students, conduct lessons based on a creative approach, carry out educational work, and solve pedagogical problems.

A primary school teacher is not only a giver of knowledge, but also a guide who opens the hearts of children, helps in their socialization, moral, aesthetic and physical development. Therefore, students studying in pedagogical higher educational institutions should pay special attention to the formation and development of their professional competencies.

In order to successfully carry out their professional activities, a teacher must have the following:

- Deep knowledge of their subject;
- Conducting lessons based on interactive methods;
- Individual approach to each student;
- Skills in planning and implementing educational work;

Formation of social and cultural activity. V.I. Baydenko described the concept of “professional competence” as follows:

-possession of knowledge, skills, qualifications and abilities necessary for activities in their specialty, as well as simultaneous autonomy and flexibility in partially solving professional problems;

-development of cooperation with colleagues in a professional interpersonal environment; an integrated combination of knowledge, characteristics and skills that allow a person to successfully perform his work in the modern work environment;

- a structure for designing standards that includes performance criteria (quality measure), scope, and required knowledge.

Summarizing the above ideas, V.I. Baydenko understands professional competence as the readiness and ability to act in accordance with the requirements of work, to independently solve the problems encountered, and at the same time to evaluate the results of one's work, that is, appropriate skills and qualifications, technical methods. Today, modern society sets the requirement for the education system to educate highly qualified, ambitious, competitive, enterprising, spiritually and physically healthy individuals. In this regard, a future primary school teacher should also have the qualities of professional competence.

Each teacher has a professional competence, which expresses the unity of theoretical and practical training in the holistic structure of the individual and characterizes his professional skills. The level of compliance of professional knowledge and skills of a particular specialty with normative requirements, levels of professional training in a particular field of activity constitute the content of professional competence. In the process of educating students, special attention is paid to the formation of professional competence in students of pedagogical universities, the creation of the necessary conditions for their choice of profession based on their capabilities and achieved level, and attention is also paid to increasing their training and personal motivation.

All this confirms the relevance of the issue of forming the foundations of pedagogical competence in modern higher education. The organization of such a system of abilities in the process contributes to the formation of professional competence of future teachers. In the process of pedagogical practice, it is necessary to consider the formation of pedagogical competence among students of pedagogical universities, the creation of the necessary conditions for their conscious choice of profession in accordance with their own capabilities, achieved level of training and personal motivation as a particularly relevant issue.

All this indicates the relevance of the issue of forming the foundations of professional competence in modern higher education, it is no exaggeration to say that. Pedagogical practice occupies a special place in the professional training of future primary school teachers. This connection between the theoretical and practical training of future specialists is the most important condition for improving the quality of their education, since practice is carried out in conditions as close as possible to future professional activities, in which the process of forming professional qualifications is carried out. Therefore, the qualifications of future primary school teachers are being successfully strengthened.

Also, pedagogical practice is an important link in the “pedagogical university - school” system, which has great opportunities for their integral cooperation, on the one hand, in improving the professional and pedagogical training of future teachers, and on the other hand, in improving the quality of teaching and upbringing. Implementing effective pedagogical dialogue is the most important component of a teacher's professional activity. Dialogue in pedagogical activity is a means of solving educational problems, a means of socio-psychological support of the educational process, a method of organizing relations between teachers and students, which determines the success of education and upbringing. A future primary school teacher should have professional competences such as building motivation in students, planning and evaluating the educational process, knowledge of information and communication technologies, regular self-improvement, psychological knowledge, and excellent knowledge of their subject.

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